

Parents' voices: inclusion of students with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities in higher education

- Summary Data -

Appendix 1. Participants (Parents) characterization according to gender

Genre	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Male	2	1	-	1	4
Female	3	5	3	7	18
Total	5	6	3	8	22

Appendix 2. Analysis of topics and dimensions

Topic	Dimension	Reference
Model	Full inclusion	O'Brien et al., 2019
	Mixed / hybrid programs	
	Segregated model	
Support	Preparation and transition from secondary to post-secondary	O'Brien et al., 2019
	Support services	
	Inclusive university tutoring	
	Volunteering	
	Digital solutions supporting inclusion in HE	
Policies	Opportunities for training & professional development	O'Brien et al., 2019
	Funding	
	Accreditation and regulations	
	Admission policy	
	Graduation policy	
Inclusive Pedagogy	Disability policy	O'Brien et al., 2019
	Universal Design for Learning (UDL)	
	Problem-based learning (PBL)	
	Service-Learning – experiences in the community	
	Transition to Profession	
	Group dynamics	
	Person Centred Planning (PCP)	
	Cooperative learning	
	Curricular Accommodations	
	(Peer) mentoring	
	Academic tutoring	
	Collaboration between teachers/tutors/mentors/academic/community/ families & other stakeholders	
	Gentle teaching	
Having safe and loving relationships		
Feeling a sense of connectedness		
Body integrity		
Feeling self-worth		
Feeling secure		
Having meaningful daily activities and a meaningful and valuable day		
Feeling inner contentment		

Planning Alternative Tomorrows with Hope (PATH)	Dreams Factors associated with successful transition Factors that constitute barriers to transition Formal transition planning Pathways transition resources	Pearpoint, Forest, & O'Brien, (1993)
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Appendix 3. Young people's age

Age	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
15 years	1	-	-	-	1
18 years	2	-	-	2	4
19 years	-	-	-	1	1
20 years	-	-	-	1	1
21 years	-	1	-	1	2
23 years	-	-	1	1	2
24 years	1	-	-	-	1
25 years	-	2	-	1	3
26 years	-	1	-	-	1
28 years	-	2	-	-	2
30 years	-	-	1	-	1
40 years	-	-	1	-	1

Appendix 4. Gender of young people

Genre	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Male	4	2	2	4	12
Female	-	4	1	3	8
Total	4	6	3	7	20

Appendix 5. Young people's education level

Education	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
6th grade	-	1	-	-	1
7th grade	2	-	-	-	2
9th grade	1	-	-	2	3
12th grade	2	4	-	2	8
Individual Educational Program (PEI)	-	5	-	2	7
Individual Specific Curriculum (CEI)	6	-	1	-	7
Regular education	1	-	-	1	2
Professional course	4	3	3	5	15

Appendix 6. Special Needs reported by parents

Special Needs	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Intellectual	4	6	3	7	20
Visual	-	1	8	-	9
Reading	1	6	1	-	8
Writing	1	4	1	-	6
Motor	-	1	5	-	6

Speech and language	-	3	-	1	4
Communication	-	3	-	1	4
Logical reasoning	1	1	-	3	5
Behavior	-	2	1	2	5
Attention	-	2	-	-	2
Hyperactivity	-	-	4	-	4
Socialization	3	-	4	-	7
Dependence on food	-	-	-	1	1

Appendix 7. Professional experience of the youngsters

Professional experience	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Greenhouse	-	-	2	-	2
Coffee shop	-	6	-	-	6
Hospital	-	-	-	4	4
Store	-	-	1	-	1
Nursing home	-	2	-	-	2
Veterinary clinic	-	1	-	-	1
Pub	2	-	-	-	2
Laundry	1	-	-	-	1
Parish Center	-	-	2	-	2
Teacher House	-	1	-	-	1
Kindergarten	-	3	-	-	3
Pastry shop	-	1	-	-	1
Drugstore	-	1	-	-	1
Supermarket	-	-	-	2	2
Restaurant	-	2	-	-	2

Appendix 8. Youngsters and parents' dreams

Dreams	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Youngs Dreams					
Continue learning	3	2	4	3	12
Have work	-	1	2	8	11
Living independently	-	4	2	1	7
Have your home	-	3	2	1	6
Have family	-	1	-	5	6
Have a driving license	-	1	-	1	2
Have a girlfriend	-	-	-	2	2
Achieve self-support	-	-	-	1	1
Be happy	5	1	2	-	8
Feel useful	-	2	-	-	2
Parents Dreams					
“Their dream is our dream”		-	2	-	2
See the happy son/daughter	1	6	-	2	9
That the son /daughter be able to support themselves	-	-	-	2	2
That son/daughter gets a job	-	1	-	2	3
That son/daughter be autonomous	1	2	1	1	5
Knowing that the son/daughter has a future	1	-	1	-	2

Appendix 9. Facilitators for a successful transition

Factors associated	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Inclusive relationships					
Affective relationships with colleagues	5	3	-	4	12
Affective relationship with teachers	4	1	2	1	8
Effective collaboration with school	2	4	1	3	9
Sharing moments of with other parents	3	2	5	1	11
Receptiveness by companies.	-	3	2	2	7
Therapies					
Physical Therapy	-	-	1	-	1
Hippotherapy	-	-	3	-	3
Speech therapy	-	-	2	1	3
Psychology	1	1	-	2	4
Specialty consultations					
Development team	2	1	-	1	4
Neuropediatric	-	-	2	1	3
Psychiatry	-	-	2	-	2
Support at school					
Multidisciplinary team	1	-	-	2	3
Special Education Teacher	7	1	3	3	14
Support teacher	1	-	3	1	5
Support from associations					
APPACDM ¹	-	4	1	-	5
APCV ²	2	-	-	-	2
ASSOL ³	-	-	-	3	3
AVISPT21 ⁴	-	2	1	7	10
<i>Pais-em-Rede</i> ⁵	-	8	8	15	31
Participation in extracurricular activities					
Theatre group	-	-	-	3	3
Sailing Club	-	-	-	2	2
Dance Club	3	-	-	-	3
Swimming	-	3	1	-	4
Activities in the association	-	3	6	5	14

Appendix 10. Barriers to transition

Factors that constitute barriers	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Activities in segregated environments	6	-	-	-	6
Bureaucratic procedures	3	-	1	1	5
Difficulties in adapting to the new environment	-	-	-	1	1
Difficulties in accessing education	4	1	5	4	14
Difficulties in accessing work	1	3	2	3	9
Difficulties in relationships with colleagues	1	-	-	10	11
Difficulties in relationship with school	6	-	-	7	13
Lack of Information	-	2	-	3	5

¹ APPACDM- *Associação Portuguesa dos Pais e Amigos do Cidadão Deficiente Mental* (Portuguese Association of Parents and Friends of the Mentally Disabled Citizen)

² APCV - Associação de Paralisia Cerebral de Viseu (Cerebral Palsy Association of Viseu)

³ ASSOL- Associação de Solidariedade Social de Lafões (Lafões Social Solidarity Association)

⁴ AVISPT21- Associação de Viseu de Portadores de Trissomia 21 (Viseu Association of Down Syndrome Patients)

⁵ Association *Pais em Rede* (Networked Parents)

Lack of inclusion	-	1	4	9	14
Lack of support	-	-	2	1	3
Lack of reception from teachers/staff at school	3	2	-	8	13
Lack of teacher preparation	2	1	-	2	5
Lack of specialized support (psychologist, speech therapist)	-	2	-	1	3
Lack of follow-up in the workplace	-	-	1	-	1
Late diagnosis	-	-	-	2	2
Pandemic situation	-	5	3	3	11

Appendix 11. Principles of Gentle Teaching

Principles of Gentle Teaching	FG1	FG2	FG3	FG4	TOTAL
Feeling safe	1	-	2	-	3
Having safe and loving relationships	1	2	2	2	7
Feeling a sense of connectedness	-	4	2	4	10
Body integrity	-	1	2	-	3
Feeling self-worth	-	3	-	1	4
Feeling secure	-	2	-	1	3
Having meaningful daily activities and a meaningful and valuable day	2	7	2	7	18

This is part of the research presented in the following paper: [REMOVED](#). Parents' voices: inclusion of students with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities in higher education. 7th conference on Smart Learning Ecosystems and Regional Development (SLERD'22)